
NASA Lunabotics: Drivetrain

Traceability Report
04/22/2025

1. Traceability Matrices

1.1 Forwards Tracing

1.1.1 Team Statement Traceability Matrix

Team Statements	Specification ID
TS1. The robot shall be capable of performing a “Full Autonomy” competition run as specified in the Lunabotics 2025 Guidebook. All subsystems shall have the required sensors and functions to complete this goal.	[BR-01] [DC-04]
TS2. The robot should have a low total mass and have a high mass-to-payload ratio	[PR-01]
TS3. The robot should be energy efficient when performing functions including navigation, excavation, and construction	[POW-01]
TS4. The robot should have enough dust protection features that dust will not have a negative effect on the robot throughout a long operation time.	[ER-01]
TS5. The robot should be capable of constructing berms of different shapes and sizes. The robot should be able to execute multiple strategies for excavating regolith.	Not applicable
TS6. The robot shall be able to go up to 0.6 m/s	[PR-02] [FR-01]
TS7. The robot shall be capable of performing a 180 degrees “zero-point” turn.	[FR-02]
TS8. The robot shall be contained within a payload envelope measuring 1.50 m x 0.75 m x 0.75 m in the initial starting configuration	[DC-01]
TS9. The robot’s initial mass shall not exceed 40kg.	[DC-02]
TS10. The target payload that the robot shall transport is 35kg.	[DC-02]
TS11. The drivetrain’s mass shall not exceed 12.5 kg.	[PR-01]
TS12. The robot shall have an Ingress Protection (IP) rating of IP6X or greater.	[ER-01]
TS13. The robot shall be able to fulfill all functional requirements without direct input from mission control center.	[BR-01] [BR-11] [BR-12] [BR-13] [BR-14] [BR-15]
TS14. The robot shall execute machine control commands autonomously.	[BR-01] [BR-11] [BR-12] [BR-13] [BR-14] [BR-15]
TS15. The robot shall not execute machine control commands from the mission control center while operating autonomously.	[BR-16] [BR-17] [BR-18] [BR-19] [BR-20]
TS16. The robot shall end autonomous operation if instructed to do so by mission control center.	[BR-09] [BR-07]

TS17. The robot shall not begin autonomous operations until instructed to do so by the mission control center.	[BR-10]
TS18. The navigation system shall be able to localize the robot within the competition arena.	[DC-04]
TS19. The robot shall regularly send telemetry data to the mission control center.	[FR-03] [IR-01] [IR-02]
TS20. The robot shall measure the power drawn by all major components.	[FR-04] [DC-04]
TS21. The power system shall utilize Flex 24v batteries to power the robot.	[POW-02]
TS22. The drivetrain shall not expend more than 18 Wh of energy in a single competition run.	[POW-01]
TS23. The old excavation method will be used. A front loader bucket is used; all the payload mass will be there, and it will stretch no more than 50 cm in front of the front of the robot. The front two wheels shall be able to withstand stresses associated; assume the center of mass is close to the front wheels.	[DC-02] [DC-03]
TS24. The old wheel design had grousers that aided in traction in regolith; the drivetrain's wheels shall contain grousers.	[DC-07]
TS25. The team also aims to optimize the size and spacing of grousers to maximize traction	[DC-07]
TS26. The chassis shall be made of 1in x 1in aluminum square tubes; the drivetrain shall be installed on the tubes.	[DC-08]
TS27. The drivetrain shall be fastened using reusable methods to make the drivetrain easier to maintain.	[MR-01]
TS28. The fasteners shall withstand the vibrations exerted by the drivetrain.	[RR-02]
TS29. The team will 3D print the wheels out of PETG.	[DC-09]
TS30. Due to the size of printers available, the maximum diameter of the wheel, grouser to grouser, is 28 cm.	[DC-10]

1.1.2 Additional Questions Traceability Matrix

Interview Report Question	Specification ID
<p>Q1: NASA's Guidelines state that the max robot mass is 80kg but the Team Statement provided said it is 40kg, can you clarify?</p> <p>Answer: While NASA allows up to 80kg, you score better if your mass is lower. That is why the team is aiming for 40kg.</p>	[DC-02]

<p>Q2. What is meant by “Zero-point” turn?</p> <p>Answer: The robot should be able to turn on the spot; the team wants the robot to stop moving forward/backwards and change its heading without of changing its location.</p>	[BR-06] [BR-07]
<p>Q3. How is turning/steering expected to be handled?</p> <p>Answer: Currently the robot has the capability to do that using differential steering, which simply uses the motors that run the wheels forward/backwards. While the team wants to maintain that option as a backup during the competition, the team also would like the drivetrain to have the ability to switch to and from swerve steering. That is when the wheels are angled in a way that minimizes skidding across the surface. Having that control over wheel direction, over the rotation of the robot if you will, be separated from the regular motors would be preferable.</p>	[BR-02] [BR-03] [BR-04] [BR-05] [BR-06] [BR-08] [FR-02] [IR-03] [IR-04]
<p>Q4. What would quantify as “regular” when it comes to sending telemetry?</p> <p>Answer: No more than half a second.</p>	[PR-03]
<p>Q5. Is the telemetry sent during the whole run or just under autonomous operations?</p> <p>Answer: Whole run, the team want to collect the data in case things go wrong</p>	[FR-03] [IR-01] [IR-02]
<p>Q6. How much stress are back wheels are expected to handle, or would they simply be identical to the front wheels?</p> <p>Answer: For simplicity of manufacturing, all 4 wheels will be the same. We plan on printing more wheels as extras, so having them all be the same is beneficial there too.</p>	[DC-02] [DC-05] [DC-06]
<p>Q7. How should the drivetrain behave if the commands stop coming in?</p> <p>Answer: If there are no new commands coming for half a second or more, regardless of what mode the robot is in, all actuators must be stopped.</p>	[RR-01]

1.1.3 NASA Guidelines Traceability Matrix

NASA Guideline Rule	Specification ID
G2.1. Volumetric dimensions - robot(s) shall be contained within a payload envelope measuring 1.50 m length x 0.75 m width x 0.75 m height. The orientation of these dimensions may be chosen by the team. It may deploy or expand beyond the envelop after the start of each attempt but shall not exceed 1.75 m in additional height (which is 2.5 m above the surface of the regolith). Multiple robot systems are allowed but the starting dimensions of the whole system (all the robots) shall comply with the volumetric dimensions given in this rule.	[DC-01]
G2.2. Robots will be inspected for the volumetric dimensions in the stowed configuration during the Safety Inspection. A “jig” frame will be placed over the rover for volume constraint verification. No modifications or team robot interaction is permitted during this verification.	[DC-01]
G2.7. The robot can run either by telerobotic (remote control) or in autonomous operations and cannot have any touch sensors to sense and avoid obstacles	[BR-01]
G4.1. The robot shall provide its own onboard power. No facility power will be provided to the robot during the attempt. There are no power limitations except that the robot must be self-powered and included in the maximum mass limit. Shall be schematically located between the battery and kill switch,[so the readings are not erased if the E-STOP button is activated. The devices shall be placed on the highest practical location on the robot and be easily visible.	[BR-13] [BR-15] [POW-02]
G5.12. Teams may not use GPS, rubber pneumatic tires; air/foam filled tires; open or closed cell foam, ultrasonic proximity sensors; or hydraulics because NASA does not anticipate the use of these on an off-world mission. This will not pass inspection,	[ER-02]
G6.4. The robot may not use any process that causes the physical or chemical properties of the regolith simulant to be changed or otherwise endangers the uniformity between competition attempts. The mining robot may not penetrate the regolith simulant surface with more force than the weight of the mining robot before the start of each competition attempt.	[ER-03]
G6.5. No ordnance, projectile, far-reaching mechanism, etc. may be used. The mining robot must move on the regolith simulant surface.	[ER-03] [FR-01] [FR-02]

1.2 Backwards Tracing

1.2.1 Requirements Definition Traceability Matrix

In this section, only the requirement ID will be shown. To see the full wording, refer to the System Requirements Specification document.

Requirement	Artifact
[FR-01]	TS6, G6.5
[FR-02]	TS7, Q3, G6.5

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[FR-03]	TS19, Q5
[FR-04]	TS20
[PR-01]	TS2, TS11
[PR-02]	TS6
[PR-03]	Q4
[DC-01]	TS8, G2.1, G2.2
[DC-02]	TS9, TS10, TS23, Q1, Q6
[DC-03]	TS23
[DC-04]	TS1, TS18, TS20
[DC-05]	Q6
[DC-06]	Q6
[DC-07]	TS24, TS25
[DC-08]	TS26
[DC-09]	TS29
[DC-10]	TS30
[ER-01]	TS4, TS12
[ER-02]	G5.12
[ER-03]	G6.4, G6.5
[RR-01]	G7
[RR-02]	TS28
[MR-01]	TS27
[POW-01]	TS3, TS22
[POW-02]	TS23, G4.1
[IR-01]	TS19, Q5
[IR-02]	TS19, Q5
[IR-03]	Q3
[IR-04]	Q3
[BR-01]	TS1, TS13, TS14, G2.7

[BR-02]	Q3
[BR-03]	Q3
[BR-04]	Q3
[BR-05]	Q3
[BR-06]	Q2, Q3
[BR-07]	Q2
[BR-08]	Q3
[BR-09]	TS16
[BR-10]	TS17
[BR-11]	TS13, TS14
[BR-12]	TS13, TS14
[BR-13]	TS13, TS14
[BR-14]	TS13, TS14, G4.1
[BR-16]	TS15
[BR-17]	TS15
[BR-18]	TS15
[BR-19]	TS15
[BR-20]	TS15

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